

Bridging FDOs and Knowledge Graphs

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Abstract. Engineering, natural- and geosciences increasingly encapsulate research data, analytical results, and software as FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) with persistent identifiers and machine-actionable metadata. In contrast, the humanities—particularly the cultural heritage domain—traditionally rely on semantically rich Linked Open Data (LOD), community ontologies, and knowledge graphs curated in collaborative environments such as Wikidata and Wikibase. As interdisciplinary research workflows now routinely combine analytical pipelines, software artefacts, 3D data, and contextual narratives, these previously distinct paradigms converge. This paper proposes a Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem that bridges FDO repositories and semantic knowledge graphs to enable interoperable discovery, provenance tracking, and reuse across domains. The approach links encapsulated FDOs with graph-based representations through shared metadata profiles and aligned ontologies, building on the NFDI Core Metadata Profile and community standards such as CIDOC CRM, PROV-O, GeoSPARQL, and the NFDIcore Ontology. Persistent identifiers form the technical interface between descriptive Linked Open Data and executable or analytical digital objects. The ecosystem is demonstrated through interdisciplinary use cases from engineering, archaeology, cultural heritage, and geosciences, including 3D models, analytical workflows, and research software. Together, these examples illustrate how combining FDO frameworks with Knowledge Graph technologies enables a machine-actionable, FAIR, and cross-disciplinary research infrastructure within the NFDI context.

Keywords: FAIR Digital Object, Linked Open Data, Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem, Cultural Heritage, Engineering

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18441544>

1 Towards a interdisciplinary Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem

Engineering, natural- and geosciences workflows typically encapsulate analysis, simulation outputs, and research software as FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) with persistent identifiers and machine-actionable metadata. In contrast, the humanities, especially the cultural-heritage domain, rely on semantically rich Linked Open Data (LOD) [8, 14, 12] and community ontologies such as CIDOC CRM, also curated in collaborative environments like Wikidata (as Wikibase instances). However, many humanities datasets now also produce research artefacts that fit the FDO paradigm, including 3D models from photogrammetry, and research software developed for data analysis and FAIRification workflows. Within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), consortia such as NFDI4Objects and NFDI4Ing address this convergence from complementary perspectives [3]. As interdisciplinary projects increasingly combine analytical results and software pipelines with narrative, contextual descriptions, diverse paradigms, LOD, Wikibase and FDO, need to merge. This contribution argues that bridging FDOs and Knowledge Graphs is essential to enable automated discovery, robust provenance, and interoperable reuse across domains. We propose a Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem that connects FDO repositories with semantic graphs to realise FAIR, reproducible, and cross-disciplinary research. The presented approach links FDO repositories with semantic Knowledge Graphs through shared metadata and common ontologies. Metadata crosswalks build on the NFDI Core Metadata Profile, which aligns DCAT, DataCite, and schema.org, ensuring that both LOD and FDOs can be described in a consistent, machine-actionable way. Ontological alignment across domains is achieved through community standards such as CIDOC CRM for cultural-heritage entities, PROV-O, GeoSPARQL, and the NFDIcore Ontology for cross-consortia interoperability. Persistent identifiers and metadata form the technical bridge between descriptive, graph-based representations and encapsulated FDOs, allowing digital artefacts such as analytical datasets, 3D models, and research software to be semantically referenced and interlinked. This integrated perspective provides the foundation for an interoperable, Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem (Fig. 1 and 2) in which both engineering and humanities data can be queried, visualised, and reused across repositories and domains. From an infrastructural perspective, the ecosystem combines distributed Knowledge Graphs, FDO registries, and community-driven ontology services into a federated architecture. RDF triplestores and Wikibase instances provide the semantic backbone for descriptive and contextual information, while labeled-property-graphs (LPG) such as Neo4J and Heterogeneous Information Networks (HINs) enable analytical and network-based views on complex datasets. FDOs stored in repositories from engineering and the humanities are connected to these graphs through persistent identifiers and shared metadata schemas, ensuring semantic and technical interoperability. Together, these components enable a federated Knowledge Graph ecosystem in which FDOs, representing measurements, 3D models, or research software, can be discovered, linked, and reused seamlessly across disciplinary and institutional boundaries. The proposed approach is demonstrated through exemplary use cases from engineering, the humanities and the geosciences, highlighting how FAIR Digital Objects can be combined with Linked Open Data within a federated Knowledge Graph ecosystem.

1. Engineering and scientific methods applied in archaeology and cultural studies inherit the research data management requirements of all scientific fields involved. The source objects and results of the research are linked in archaeology and cultural studies through metadata and authority data. The data generated and the code used follow the rules of engineering and scientific research data management and are incorporated, for example, into the knowledge graph of NFDI4ING. The documentation of the process chain, as exemplified here by

a daylight simulation in a Roman building in Ostia, is of particular importance (Fig. 3). Data and code must be stored as FAIR digital objects, which means, among other things, that they must be available in open file formats or FOSS and described in sufficient detail by metadata to enable reuse.

2. Linked Open Ogham integrates RDF/LOD representations of early medieval inscriptions within the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph (Fig. 4), Wikidata and other Wikibase instances such as FactGrid, the fuzzy-sl Wikibase, and Semantic Kompakkt (Fig. 5), interlinked with 3D annotations and spatial data from OpenStreetMap. Associated FDOs include 3D models of Ogham stones generated through professional photogrammetry within the OG(H)AM and Ogham in 3D projects and FDOs as research software for FAIRification workflows – such as CSV-to-RDF converters, QuickStatements tools for Wikibase integration, and Python/Jupyter scripts for querying and visualising SPARQL results (Fig. 6).
3. The Govan Stones in Scotland (Glasgow) are similarly represented as LOD and Wikibase data (Fig. 7), complemented by FDOs as 3D models derived from a PhD thesis [6] and citizen-science photogrammetry.
4. In the Campanian Ignimbrite use case, geoscientific findspots are modelled as LOD with the fuzzy-sl Ontology and stored in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase, while related FDOs include Python transformation scripts from CSV to RDF (Fig. 8) and Jupyter notebooks for visualising findspots, as well as Python Scripts used for tephra and sediment EPMA and LA-ICP-MS analyses data from the Eifel region.
5. The implementation of (A) the Alligator method [11] to calculate a relative chronology according to Allen and Freksa [1, 2, 4, 5] and RDF data to display the results as well as the calculation from an initial correspondence analysis as well as (B) the JavaScript reasoning implementation within the Academic Meta Tool (AMT) [10] to derive new knowledge on vague information in RDF-based knowledge graphs are two examples for research software as data and research artefact [9], capsulated in an FDO.

Together, these examples demonstrate how descriptive Linked Open Data, analytical datasets, 3D models, and research software can be connected through FDO frameworks and Knowledge Graph technologies to form a machine-actionable, interdisciplinary research infrastructure. By bridging the humanities' semantic expressiveness with the engineering focus on machine-actionable FDOs, this approach contributes to a shared understanding of how FDOs and Knowledge Graphs can co-evolve within a federated research infrastructure. It demonstrates that combining persistent, encapsulated data objects with ontology-based semantic layers enhances findability, provenance tracking, and automated interoperability across disciplines. Ultimately, the integration of FDOs and Knowledge Graphs within the NFDI ecosystem offers a sustainable model for connecting research data, software, and analytical processes, turning disciplinary silos into a machine-actionable web of interlinked, FAIR scientific objects.

Data availability statement

- Linked Open Ogham: <https://github.com/LinkedOpenOgham/ogham-lod>
- Ogham/Govan 3D-Data: <https://sketchfab.com/b-unicycling/collections>

- Ogham in Wikidata: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Irish_Ogham_Stones
- Govan 3D-Data: <https://skfb.ly/6XTQr>
- Jupyter Notebooks: <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/jupyter-nb-lod>
- CI Transformation Scripts: <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/>
- Alligator: <https://github.com/leiza-rse/alligator>
- Academic Meta Tool Reasoning: <https://github.com/leiza-rse/amt-playground/blob/master/docs/amt.js>

Author contributions

Authors' contributions according to the CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy). Conceptualisation: all authors; Data Curation: all authors; Formal Analysis: all authors; Methodology: all authors; Resources: all authors; Software: FT, AN; Writing – original draft: FT, AN; Writing – review & editing: FT, AN.

Funding

This work is funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under the National Research Data Infrastructure. DFG project numbers: NFDI4ING (442146713) and NFDI4Objects (501836407). Some works were funded by Wikimedia Deutschland, Open Science Fellow Program 2020/21: "Irische Ogham Steine im Wikimedia Universum". Both PhD theses from F. Schenk and K.N. Kasten were supported from Johannes-Gutenberg University in Mainz and University of Glasgow. Ms. Kasten's thesis was also funded by the College of Arts Scholarship and the Centre for Scottish and Celtic Studies Seedcorn Fund. The work on Alligaor and AMT is supported by the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA) and the Mainz Centre for Digitality in the Humanities and Cultural Studies (mainzed).

Figure 1: The Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem. Florian Thieri and Andras Noback, CC BY 4.0.

Figure 2: Legend for the different spheres. Florian Thieri, CC BY 4.0.

Figure 3: Scheme of the documentation of the process chain, here by a daylight simulation in a Roman building in Ostia. © Andreas Noback.

Figure 4: Schema for visualising a query of the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph for Irish Ogham stones, using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin and Ogham Stones on the Dingle Peninsula (A-C). Images: Florian & Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0; maps: © OpenStreetMap contributors.

Figure 5: Semantic Kompakkt visualisation of CIIC 81. 3D-model: b-unicycling, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0; object: Located at the Stone Corridor at University College Cork, OSM node 3664696256.

Figure 6: Ogham Visualisations using a Python Jupyter Minion. Florian Thieri, CC BY 4.0.

The image displays the Semantic Kompaktt interface for the 'Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)'. At the top, there are navigation buttons for 'New object' and 'New collection'. Below this, a toolbar includes 'Linguistich', 'Annotate', and various editing tools. The main content area features a 3D model of the stone on the left, a descriptive text block in the center, and a photograph of the stone in a museum setting on the right. The text block reads: 'Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks and is the best preserved.' Below the text are links for 'Related agents', 'Creation', 'External Links', and 'Related object structure'. The bottom section shows the Wikibase data page for 'Govan Stone 02 (Hogback) (Q1772)', which includes a table of language labels, a table of statements, and a list of external links and references.

Figure 7: Hogback Govan Stone 2 at Govan Old Parish Church, Glasgow, Scotland and modelling in Semantic Kompaktt. 3D-data by Megan N. Kasten, CC BY 4.0; photo: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.

Figure 8: Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) sites created using the SPARQLing Unicorn Research Toolkit with findspots from [7, 13] CC BY 4.0, Florian Thierly & Fiona Schenk.

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